

ISSUES OF INCREASING THE INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY OF CIVIL SOCIETY INSTITUTIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL ACTIVITY AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE

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Annotation: This article examines the issues of increasing the innovative activity of civil society institutions in national-spiritual development.

Keywords: Legal awareness, political activism, spiritual maturity, spiritual heritage, interfaith tolerance, civil society, public control, public chamber.

Today, a free and developed civil society, a "society of knowledge", the principles of democratic and sustainable development are widely applied to life, human capital becomes one of the decisive factors of development, the establishment of free market relations, the rapid penetration of information and communication technologies into all aspects of the life of society and the state. global features such as arrival are gaining priority. The changes of the era are taking place all over the world, the process of globalization, mixing of cultures. This complex process affects not only young people, but also the outlook of adults. Such intense political changes, renewals, the achievements of our multinational country in the material and spiritual life, and the fact that it has become an important factor of the democratization of society in harmony with the growth of national revival, requires knowledge of its legal processes. enriching the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations with positive aspects and thereby improving national-cultural revival. In today's process of

globalization, the democratization of political and cultural life and the activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations, their social well-being are of great importance in the implementation of social, cultural, spiritual and educational work. It is important to study its role from a political-philosophical point of view, which is gaining a new meaning. Political changes and updates in society, the achievements of our multi-ethnic country in the material and spiritual life, and the fact that it has become an important factor of democratization of society in harmony with the growth of national revival, require knowledge of its legal processes. In the process of globalization, to study advanced foreign experience in deepening political and cultural reforms in society and to enrich them with the positive aspects of the activities of civil society institutions , thereby improving national cultural revival. ordinary _ It is intended to approach the problem from the point of view of today's reality, the democratization of socio-political processes, and the formation of civil society institutions. found "Such immortal masterpieces testify to the existence of a great culture in this ancient land, in the soil where we live today." Faith in the intelligence of a person, the idea of becoming a nation and achieving happiness together were praised by Eastern thinkers such as al-Khwarazmi, al-Farabi, Beruni Ibn Sina. A person can reach such perfection only by helping each other, by joining together many people in the place where they deliver a share of things. He is worthy of such perfection according to his nature. Such a society is the sum of the activities of all its members, and it provides everything that everyone needs to live and reach maturity." Naturally, the achievements of mankind in material and spiritual life are considered a unique form of culture, and they are expressed in almost all the researches of the scholars of the East. In his works "India" and "Relics of Ancient Nations", Beruni commented on the holidays, customs and traditions of different nations. "Cultural society and cultural city will be such that every person from the population of this country will be free in the profession, everyone will be engaged

in the profession that he wants and chooses. People will be truly free. One will not be the master of another. Among them, various good habits, pleasures and pleasures will appear." Also, the scientists of the Commonwealth of Nations countries have implemented the processes of civil society, political cultural life, and democratization. There is no society in human history that has not considered or cared about its successors and future generations. This issue is of particular importance for Uzbekistan. Today, the role of civil society institutions in increasing the socio-political activity of young people is considered important. After all, only a healthy nation and a healthy generation can build a great country in the future. After all, another main goal of increasing the spiritual maturity and socio-political activity of young people is to form their thinking of living with a sense of responsibility for the future of the country, people, nation, and destiny. Therefore, any change, first of all, in the minds of people, will create a chance for the social, political and economic activity of people, especially young people, to increase in the development of society.

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